
TEACHING GERMAN GRAMMAR TO STUDENTS IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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Abstract.

The article is devoted to modern digital technologies that contribute to the mastery of complex grammatical phenomena in the German language. The recommendations given by the author will help make the learning process motivating, interesting and exciting.

Keywords.

generation, grammar, learning, digital technologies, creativity.

Introduction.

In the process of teaching foreign languages, the study of grammar has always been given great attention. In the 19th century, when the grammar-translation method dominated, this aspect of the language was considered as the main tool for mastering a foreign language. In the process of developing methods of teaching foreign languages, the role of grammar has somewhat decreased. At the present stage, it is considered as a necessary and important aspect of learning a foreign language, which ensures correct speaking, understanding and writing [33, 59].

Main part

Possession of grammatical norms and the ability to apply them, that is, the formed grammatical competence is considered as one of the conditions for the successful implementation of the professional activities of specialists who have to interact with foreign partners, to carry out written and oral communication. Clear speech and writing are the calling card of a specialist and contributes to the solution of many problems. It should be noted that most of today's students are typical representatives of generation Z or "zoomers". They were born already in the digital world, grew up in the era of fast Internet, got used to being mobile, not being tied to a place and time.

Generation Z owns IT technologies, values diversity and inclusiveness, is results-oriented, easily breaks the rules, believes that everyone is equal and,

therefore, is more active than millennials in expressing their opinions on social issues. In addition, zoomers live by the principle: "Self-development is fashionable.

Life is good when it is diverse. Work should be fun." These conditions determine not only the way of life of digital people, but also their approach and attitude to learning. Teachers, in turn, cannot disregard the above characteristics, but on the contrary, they must take into account and actively apply them when organizing the educational process. With regard to the study of a foreign language, in particular grammar, it is justified to take into account openness to the new and unusual on the part of students, their mobility and creativity. As we know, grammar as an aspect of the language studies its structure and rules, plays an organizing role. For a long time, training was based on the principle of presenting grammatical rules in the form of a text or a table, performing exercises and monitoring the learned material.

Traditionally, most textbooks have presented rules out of the box, without using any element of search or deduction. The modern approach to the methodology of teaching foreign languages highlights the independent activity of students, because, as experience shows, those rules that were derived independently and the material that was refracted according to the characteristics of their memory are best absorbed. Modern textbooks implement the above approach.

The introduction of grammatical structures is carried out through texts for reading or listening. After checking the global or search reading (listening), students are asked to reconstruct the statement or memorize the table and use the key words to derive the rule themselves. This is followed by exercises to fill in the gaps or reproduce the phrase. After that, the grammatical structure is reflected in the productive types of speech activity: speaking and writing, and serves to fulfill communication goals. It is important that in the process of work "linguistic attention" is activated, individual characteristics of memory are taken into account and the transfer of previously acquired knowledge is stimulated either from the native language or from a foreign language studied earlier.

Modern methodologists propose to optimize the traditional approach to teaching grammar. Instead of ready-made grammar references or along with them, students are encouraged to write their own grammars, where a large number of symbols, supports and associations can be used, sometimes understandable only to the author himself. As we know, representatives of Generation Z are visuals. It is better for them to present any information in a visual and attractive way, it is best

that the picture moves and is dynamic. Stories and reading long texts do not attract buzzers. It is recommended not to overload them with a large amount of information, everything should be immediately clear and "cling" [37,135].

The material should remain in memory without much effort, almost involuntarily. This requires teachers to rethink the learning process. It is advisable to use various "life hacks", i.e. a set of techniques, tricks, useful tips to simplify the process of achieving your goals. In the methodology of teaching German, there are already many ready-made "life hacks" for mastering German grammar.

One of the biggest difficulties in learning the German language is memorizing the articles of nouns, which are extremely important not only for the formation of the forms of the noun itself, but also for mastering the system of adjective declension, replacing nouns with a pronoun, forming and using possessive and demonstrative pronouns. Often the gender of nouns in Russian/Uzbek and German does not match, this leads to interference and a large number of errors.

So, for example, the correctness of the grammatical exercises can be checked by the keys. Exercises that involve the independent use of certain grammatical structures can be performed orally, recorded on a smartphone voice recorder, and an audio recording can be sent to the teacher in the Viber or WhatsApp application. Internet resources provide invaluable opportunities for the formation and improvement of grammatical competence today [9, 288].

With the resource "Grammatiktraining.de" students can train their grammar skills online. The range of topics presented here can be used at various stages of learning. Students can independently familiarize themselves with the rules, perform exercises and tests.

Übungen, Spiele und Tests zur deutschen Grammatik

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[Grammatikübungen online](#)

- Sie finden eine Vielzahl von Online Übungen zu Themen der deutschen Grammatik. Es handelt sich um Texteingabe-Übungen, Schreibübungen, Multiple-Choice-Übungen, Drag and Drop-Übungen und um Grammatikspiele.
- Diese Übungen sollen Spaß machen und Ihnen helfen, Ihre Kenntnisse der deutschen Grammatik zu verbessern.
- Wenn Sie eine dieser Online-Übungen machen wollen, klicken Sie [hier](#).

[Übungen für die Schule](#)

- Die Seite <http://el-deutsch.de/schule/menu.html> auf el-deutsch.de ist für Schülerinnen und Schüler der 3. und 4. Klasse Grundschule.
- Die Spiele und Übungen auf der Seite sollen Spaß machen und beim Lernen helfen.

[Basisgrammatik](#)

- Es geht um wichtige Begriffe der deutschen Grammatik.
- Dieses Thema ist vor allem dann wichtig für Sie, wenn Sie nicht wissen, was beispielsweise ein Infinitiv oder eine Präposition ist.
- Erklärungen, Grammatikvideos und Übungen zur Basisgrammatik finden Sie [hier](#).

The Grammatikdeutsch.de Internet resource with a variety of online exercises on grammar and spelling helps to improve knowledge of grammar.

The resource "Mein-deutschbuch.de" has proven itself well. Online exercises are presented here by levels (A1-B2) and allow you to train those aspects that cause the greatest difficulty (conjugation of strong and weak verbs, the use and declension of articles, the declension of adjectives, etc.).

Students also respond positively to the following sites: www.deutschlernen.com, www.babbel.com, www.mydailygerman.com.

Speaking about students of generation Z, one cannot help but dwell on such an aspect as gamification. Zoomers play a lot, willingly, and this feature can be successfully used in the learning process. The introduction of an element of competition and competition contributes to the activation of educational and cognitive activities, and medialization allows to diversify everyday life and eliminate boredom, because emotions should be an integral part of classes.

Conclusion:

Students willingly plunge into unusual situations; change their usual roles, looking at problems from a different perspective. This means the content; situations and tasks in the exercises should be provocative and allow room for creativity and creativity. Thus, we can say that teaching grammar has been and remains an important aspect of teaching foreign languages. However, today's generation of zoom students approaches the study of this aspect in a new way and requires the teacher to optimize the learning process, more ingenuity, an individual approach and the use of an emotional factor.

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